

Automated mineralogy application (TIMA system) in exploration and economic geology – examples from Polish targets and deposits

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Automated mineralogy techniques have been developed intensively in recent decades, including technical and software improvements. It is a very fast and robust method utilized by both academia and industry in many stages along the value chain of the mineral raw materials. During mineral exploration it is used for fast and thorough rock characterization (ore minerals identification, mineral associations-alterations, visualization of textures and structures, etc.), in active mines for ore quality control and recognition of mineralogy and chemistry of the newly developed part of the deposits, during mineral processing stage it is indispensable as grain size and shape, mineral liberation, mineralogy and chemistry of a large set of samples can be measured in a very fast and efficient way.

The TIMA automated mineralogy system is used at AGH University of Krakow in cooperation with the TESCAN company since 2020. It has been employed in several EU founded projects (EIT RM MinExTarget, Horizon Europe AVANTIS), internal research projects, and student master thesis. A few conclusions from those projects are presented here.

Analyses of the Heavy Mineral Concentrates (HMC) from recent river sediments from the Karkonosze Izera Massif were tested as a tool for tracking tin mineralization. Fast samples scanning allowed to identify the mineral composition of HMC, which helps with cassiterite grain selection for further EMPA and LA-ICP-MS analyses. A brief interpretation of the rutile chemistry confirmed several rutile generations. Analyses of size and shape of selected heavy minerals help with interpretations of sources and transportation patterns.

The processing of the Fe-Ti-V ores from Krzemianka deposit is demanding and one of the reasons why the deposit is currently considered uneconomic. Application of the TIMA system for the analyses of the products of the selective fragmentation of the Krzemianka ore allowed to quantify how efficient each technique (e.g., Selfrag, HPGR) is and to track the element deportment. The data illustrates in a very simple way mineral liberation and size of the fragmented ore, that helps to choose the most efficient method of fragmentation (included mineral liberation ratio, energy efficiency, etc.).

Besides many advantages of this method the most important conclusion is that the quality of the obtained data highly depend on data interpretation and in this sense the process of data acquisition is “automated” but the quality of the result is highly depend on the skills and the experience of the operator.

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